

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTIBIOTICS AGAINST SOME DISEASES

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Abstract: The main functions of the heart are regulated by the sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions of the autonomic nervous system. In general, the sympathetic nerves of the heart are facilitatory, while the parasympathetic (vagus) nerves are inhibitory. The kinetics of the two autonomous cleavages are significantly different. Vagal effects develop very quickly, often within a heartbeat, and they also decay quickly. Thus, the vagus nerve has the ability to control the activity of the heart. On the contrary, the onset and decay of sympathetic influences is much more gradual; only small changes are made during one cardiac cycle. When two autonomous systems act simultaneously, the effects are not algebraically additive, but complex interactions prevail.

Key words: Antibiotic, infection, disease, resistant, dose, nerve, synapse, bacterial, drug, analgesic, prescription.

Purpose of research. The purpose of our research is to determine the reason for the use of antibiotics in various diseases and the effectiveness of antibiotics.

The urgency of the problem. Antibiotics are used to treat bacteria that enter the body and cause infection. However, due to the mistaken belief that antibiotics are a quick cure for all diseases, blindly taking antibiotics often when they are not needed is causing serious consequences.

Material and inspection methods. Antibiotics should be taken exactly as prescribed by the doctor, and the dose of antibiotics should not be reduced or stopped at will. When antibiotic resistance develops due to careless misuse or poor medical judgment, antibiotics cannot effectively suppress disease-causing bacteria. The misuse and abuse of antibiotics leads to the proliferation of resistant bacteria, so antibiotics should be avoided as much as possible unless absolutely necessary for an infectious disease caused by the bacteria. Below we want to talk about the use and effectiveness of antibiotics in several types of diseases:

Febril- Antibiotics are not required unless a bacterial infection is evident and there are no symptoms other than fever. Therefore, it is more effective to take antipyretic analgesics that relieve body pain and reduce fever, rather than antibiotics for simple fever symptoms. If you have a fever without other symptoms such as coughing, shortness of breath, vomiting, or diarrhea, it can be treated without medication. However, if the temperature of 38 degrees and above lasts for more than 72 hours or the pain is severe, antipyretic analgesics should be taken.

Over 80-90% of colds are caused by viruses. Antibiotics are effective against bacterial infections and ineffective against viral infections. Therefore, antibiotics are useless for colds, and antibiotics are ineffective for preventing complications such as pneumonia. However, if a secondary bacterial infection occurs, such as a sore throat, pneumonia, or bronchitis, a doctor's prescription may require antibiotics.

Cough. Antibiotics do not work for coughs caused by viruses. However, antibiotics are used for coughs caused by infections such as pertussis, mycoplasma, and chlamydia. Symptoms of whooping cough are usually no fever, no cough during the day, but paroxysmal cough and vomiting at night. Mycoplasma and chlamydia infections are characterized by a strong cough. Sometimes pneumonia causes a cough, and in this case also antibiotics are needed.

Runny nose. A runny nose is rarely directly related to germs. Therefore, in most cases, antibiotics are not necessary for a clear runny nose. Clear nasal mucus that is runny and sometimes yellow or green is caused by normal bacteria, white blood cells, and secretions and does not require antibiotics. However, when light brown purulent mucus discharges due to bacterial sinusitis, this is a sign that the sinusitis is rapidly worsening, so antibiotics are needed.

Acute otitis media. Inflammation from a sore throat or nose can spread through the Eustachian tube to the ear, causing a bacterial infection. This is especially common in children with a wide and short eustachian tube connected to the nose. In this case, antibiotics may be necessary, but long-term use of antibiotics to prevent infection is not recommended due to the risk of antibiotic resistance.

Urinary tract infections. Urinary tract infections such as cystitis and urethritis are more common than viral infections. Antibiotics work better than other diseases, so it is important to use antibiotics as prescribed by your doctor.

Enteritis More than 90% of common enteritis in children is an infection by viruses such as rota or adeno. Therefore, the symptoms should be eliminated with antipyretic and analgesic prescriptions, not antibiotics. On the other hand, antibiotics are needed for bacterial enteritis, which results in bloody or mucous stools.

Summary. In conclusion, antibiotics have negative and positive effects on the body. When taking antibiotics, it is necessary to carefully study the side effects of the antibiotic according to the doctor's prescription. Using antibiotics without a doctor's prescription or when antibiotics are not needed can lead to negative consequences. Therefore, it is necessary to take a sample from the place of suspected infection (for example: urine, sputum, feces, blood, etc.), carry out necessary analyzes such as bacterial tests, and then use antibiotics.

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